

Monoterpenoids. Part III.* Ring Enlargement of Tetrahydrocarvone†

T. M. Jacob and Sukh Dev**

Ring-expansion of tetrahydrocarvone has been studied by the diazomethane method and by the Tiffeneau-Demjanov semipinacolic deamination. The first method yielded a mixture of ketones (30%) consisting of 2-methyl-5-isopropylsuberone (~44%) and 3-methyl-6-isopropylsuberone (~56%); formation of the spiro- α -epoxide to the extent of 28% took place. The semipinacolic deamination method also, as anticipated, yielded an identical mixture of the suberones.

2-Methyl-5-isopropylsuberone (I) and 3-methyl-6-isopropylsuberone (II) are important intermediates in certain azulene synthesis (Jacob and Sukh Dev, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1956, 576; Dutta, *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 761) and their systematic syntheses have been described (Jacob and Sukh Dev, *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 327; cf. Dutta, *ibid.*, 1956, 33, 885). The present investigation was undertaken to ascertain the ratio of (I) and (II) resulting in a ring-expansion reaction of tetrahydrocarvone (III).

Ring Enlargement by Diazomethane

This method of ring-expansion has recently been reviewed (Gutsche, "Organic Reactions", 1954, 8, 364). The reaction was carried out by the nitrosomethylurethane method, according to the general directions of Meerwein (German Patent 579,309).

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† Abstracted from the Ph.D thesis (Madras, 1956) of T. M. Jacob.

** Present address: National Chemical Laboratory, Poona-8.

The yield of the ring-expanded material was about 30% and about 28% of the starting ketone was recovered; formation of the oxide (IV) to the extent of 28% was demonstrated by hydrolysis to the glycol (V). The composition of the suberone fraction was established as 44%(I) and 56%(II) by quantitative infrared spectrophotometry (*vide infra*).

Ring Enlargement by the Tiffeneau Rearrangement

The Tiffeneau rearrangement (Tiffeneau, Weil, and Tchoubar, *Compt. rend.*, 1937, 205, 54; Tchoubar, *ibid.*, 1941, 212, 195; *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1949, 160, 164, 169), which is a special case of the Demjanov reaction, has sometimes been used with advantage for the ring-expansion of cyclic ketones (Ruzicka, Plattner, and Wild, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1943, 26, 1631; Gutsche, *J. Amer. Chem.*, 1949, 71, 3513; Cope, Nace, and Estes, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 1123; Dauben *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 2359; Roberts and Gorham, *ibid.*, 1952, 74, 2278; Blicke and co-workers, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 2924, 5418; Wendler, Taub, and Slates, *ibid.*, 1955, 77, 3559). Tetrahydrocarvone (III) was converted into the cyanohydrin and thence to the acetate (VI) in an overall yield of 99%. The reduction of the cyanohydrins with lithium aluminium hydride has been reported (Nace and Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1952, 74, 1861), but we have preferred to use the acetate for reduction in order to reduce chances for the formation of any tetrahydrocarvol through a retrogression (under alkaline conditions of the reaction) of the cyanohydrin and subsequent reduction of the resulting ketone (cf. H. C. Neumann, E. T. H. Dissertation, Zürich, 1949). The same situation can, however, arise if the reduction of the acetate function occurred first (Roberts and Gorham, *loc. cit.*). The yield of the ring-expanded material was 70%; the glycol (V) could also be isolated to the extent of 12%.

In a previous publication (Jacob and Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*) it has been pointed out that the ketone (I) has two characteristic bands at 915 and 893 cm^{-1} and these could be utilised for their estimation* in a mixture. The infrared spectra of the ketone-mixture, obtained by the two methods, were almost superimposable. The percentage of the ketone (I) in the mixture was estimated from its absorption at 893 cm^{-1} and that of ketone (II) from its absorption at 865 cm^{-1} , by following the usual procedure (e.g. *vide* Tunnicliff *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 890). The results show that the suberone mixtures, obtained in both the processes, contain 44% (I) and 56% (II).

The migration of the groups in a molecular rearrangement is governed by stereo-electronic factors. In the case under study, the formation of (I) or (II) will depend on which of the bonds (*i.e.*, the residual groups with its bonding electrons) (*a*) or (*b*) moves. It would appear that in the present instance, electronic factors being almost identical[†], the movement will be essentially determined by steric factors.

The intermediate, resulting from the nucleophilic attack of diazomethane on the carbonyl group, can be represented as a diazonium betain (Arndt and Eistert, *Ber.*, 1935, 68,

* In an attempt to use the method of vapour-phase chromatography for this analysis, it was found that both the ketones had the same retention times under a variety of experimental conditions (temperature, column, gas, etc.).

† The present results could possibly be explained by a slight preference of the bond (*b*) to migration due to the induction effect of the methyl group. That this is not so, is clear from several examples in the literature (e.g. *vide* Wendler, Taub, and Slates, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 3559; Birch and Harrison, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1955, 8, 519) in which the methylene group has preferentially migrated.

196). Since, a similar intermediate has been postulated in the reaction of nitrous acid with β -amino alcohol (Mckenzie and Richardson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 122, 79) it was anticipated, as actually realised, that the Tiffeneau rearrangement would yield a mixture of ketones, essentially identical with that obtained in the dizomethane reaction. The decomposition of the intermediate can occur either by a synchronous electron-transfer process or by a stepwise sequence involving a carbonium ion. Sufficient evidence has been gathered (McCasland, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2293; Curtin and Crew, *ibid.*, 1955, 77, 354; Curtin and Schmukler, *ibid.*, 1955, 77, 1155; Ramirez and Stafiej, *ibid.*, 1956, 78, 644; Curtin, *Record Chem. Prog.*, 1954, 15, 111) to show that in the nitrous acid deamination of β -amino alcohols, the nitrogen-release occurs through a concerted one-step process, involving a back-side attack on the carbon bearing the diazonium groups. Probably the same path is followed by the diazomethane ring-enlargement reaction (Robinson and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 371). Two configurations (VIII) and (IX) are possible for the transition state in the ring-expansion of carvomenthone*, which meet the requirements of the principle of the coplanarity of the centres involved in a synchronous reaction (Barton and Miller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1066; Barton and Rosenfelder, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1048).

(VIII)

(IX)

Configuration (VIII) will lead to the suberone (I) and (IX) would result in (II). In the configuration (VIII), the relatively bulky diazonium group is placed skew to the oxygen and the $-\text{CHCH}_3$ on the next carbon, whereas in (IX), it is skew to the oxygen and the $-\text{CH}_2$, and a hydrogen atom becomes skew to the oxygen and the $-\text{CHCH}_3$ group; thus the conformation in (IX) would be energetically favoured, at least, to some extent. The energy-differences of (VIII) and (IX) cannot, however, be large and in the ring-expansion reaction, a small excess of (II), as actually realised, is to be expected.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used for drying the extracts. The infrared measurements were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer double-beam instrument with sodium chloride optics.

*The tetrahydrocarvone used in these experiments has been estimated to be at least 75% (-)-carvomenthone (Read and Johnston, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1934, 226). The bulkier diazonium methyl group has been shown in the equatorial conformation; the treatment discussed can apply equally well, and with similar results, to the other epimer.

Action of Diazomethane on Tetrahydrocarvone.—A mixture of tetrahydrocarvone (77.4 g., 0.5 *M*) (Jacob and Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1957, 24, 332), anhydrous aldehyde-free methanol (200 c.c.), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) was placed in a 3-necked flask (1 litre) fitted with a stirrer, thermometer, dropping funnel, and an exit tube. Nitrosomethylurethane (50 c.c., 63.3 g., 0.48 *M*) was added to the above stirred mixture during 5 to 6 hours, the temperature of the reaction having been maintained at 20–25° by suitably cooling the flask, when required. After leaving overnight (16 hours) as such, the product was filtered from potassium carbonate and the low-boiling material distilled (water-bath 50 mm). The residue was fractionated through an efficient column to give: (i) b.p. 84–88°/5 mm. mostly at 84°, n_D^{25} 1.4350–1.4570, yield 45 g.; (ii) b.p. 88–95°/5 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4580, yield 4.2 g.; (iii) b.p. 95–98°/5 mm, chiefly at 98°, n_D^{25} 1.4610–1.4620, yield 25 g.; (iv) a residue.

The third fraction represented the ring-expanded material. It was redistilled to give a product: b.p. 98°/5 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4616, [α] $_D^{25}$ -12°.6. (Found: C, 78.17; H, 11.78. $C_{11}H_{20}O$ requires C, 78.57; H, 11.91%.)

The first fraction was a mixture of tetrahydrocarvone and the oxide (IV). This was established as follows: This material (3.85 g) was stirred at room temperature (20–25°) with 4% H_2SO_4 (50 c.c.) for 64 hours, then saturated with ammonium sulphate and extracted with ether (15 c.c. $\times$ 5). After drying, the solvent was removed and the residue fractionated to give a fore-run (b.p. 68–75°/2 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4550, yield 1.15 g.), identified as tetrahydrocarvone, and a high-boiling product, b.p. 158–65°/2 mm. n_D^{25} 1.4780, yield 2.0 g. The latter was fractionated and the cut with b.p. 160°/2 mm., n_D^{25} 1.4800 analysed. It gave a positive test with periodic acid (Shriner and Fuson, "The Systematic Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1948, p. 115). (Found: C, 70.75; H, 11.8. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 70.98; H, 11.82%.)

In this experiment when excess of nitrosomethylurethane (1.6 *M* for 1 *M* of tetrahydrocarvone) was used, the yield of the ring-expanded material was 45% (based on the ketone).

1-Cyano-2-methyl-5-isopropylcyclohexyl Acetate (VI).—To well-cooled (ice-salt) tetrahydrocarvone (15.3 g., 0.1 *M*) liquid hydrogen cyanide (7.5 c.c., 0.18 *M*) was added all at once. To this powdered potassium cyanide (0.1 g.) and diethylamine (2 drops) were added. The reaction mixture was kept at 0 to 5° for 24 hours, chilled to -5°, and the base neutralised with phosphoric acid (*d* 1.75, 1 c.c.). The product was diluted with anhydrous ether (20 c.c.) and a chilled mixture of acetic anhydride (25 c.c.) and acetyl chloride (1.5 c.c.) added. This was left aside at 0° for 48 hours and then at room temperature (20–25°) for one week. The excess of acetic anhydride, etc. was removed (column) and the residue was carefully fractionated to obtain the required compound as a colorless liquid, b.p. 120°/2 mm, $n_D^{24.5}$ 1.4535–1.4605, yield 22.1 g. (99.7%).

An analytical sample had: n_D^{24} 1.4595, d_4^{25} 0.9895, M_D 61.66 (calc. 61.44). (Found: N, 6.7. $C_{13}H_{21}O_2N$ requires N, 6.3%.)

1-Hydroxy-2-methyl-5-isopropylcyclohexylmethylamine (VII).—Lithium aluminium hydride (7.2 g., 0.19 *M*) was placed in a one-litre 3-necked flask, and at once covered with anhydrous ether (250 c.c.). This was stirred under anhydrous conditions to get a fine slurry (1/2 hour). A solution of the cyanohydrin acetate (19.2 g., 0.086 *M*) in ether (80 c.c.) was let in with stirring at a rate that the refluxing could be controlled (20 minutes). After gently refluxing for 1½ hours, the reaction mixture was left overnight (16 hours). The reaction

mixture was well-chilled in ice-salt and the excess of lithium aluminium hydride destroyed by the addition of ice-water (20 c.c.). To this a solution of sodium potassium tartrate (20%, 500 c.c.) was added to decompose the complex. After stirring for 1 hour at room temperature, the turbid solution was extracted with ether (100 c.c. $\times$ 5) and the extract dried. The solvent was flashed off, the last traces under suction on a water bath. The crude amine (16. g., 100.4%), thus obtained, was directly used for the next step.

Deamination with Nitrous Acid.—The above crude amine (16 g.) was dissolved in water (110 c.c.) containing acetic acid (8 c.c.); a slight insoluble material was removed. To this solution, well cooled in ice, a solution of sodium nitrite (8 g., 0.12 *M*) in water (50 c.c.) was added during 20 minutes with stirring. The stirring was continued for another 2½ hours at 0° and then for ¼ hour at room temperature (25°), and finally on a steam-bath for 45 minutes. The cooled reaction mixture was extracted with ether (50 c.c. $\times$ 5), washed with brine, and dried. After removal of the solvent the residue was fractionated: (i) b.p. 110-19°/40 mm, n_D^{28} 1.4575 yield 0.7 g.; (ii) b.p. 119-24°/40 mm, n_D^{28} 1.4595, yield 4.2 g.; (iii) b.p. 125-28°/40 mm, n_D^{28} 1.4615, yield 5.9 g.; (iv) 120-60°/2 mm, n_D^{28} 1.4850, yield 1.92 g.

The first fraction was rejected. Fractions (ii) and (iii) represented the ring-expanded material. These cuts were mixed up and precisely refractionated to remove some alcohol impurity (infrared absorption at 3521 cm^{-1} ; possibly tetrahydrocarvol), when it had b.p. 97-98°/5 mm. (Found: C, 78.53; H, 11.92. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 78.57; H, 11.91%).

The fourth fraction was redistilled to give a viscous liquid, b.p. 150-55°/1 mm, n_D^{28} 1.4850; it gave a positive test with periodic acid. (Found: C, 71.06.; H, 11.83. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 70.98; H, 11.82%).